

**FROM THE EXPERIENCE OF CREATING NEW MULTIPLE-VARIATE
PROBLEMS AND TASKS IN THE SCIENCE OF THEORETICAL
MECHANICS**

Professor t.m. **Makhmudov Zokirjon Sotivoldievich**,
Senior Lecturer **Najmiddinov Insomiddin Biloliddinovich**
Namangan Engineering-Construction Institute

Abstract: In our country, in recent years, due to modern requirements, the number of higher educational institutions and the number of students admitted to them has increased sharply. As a result, the issue of providing students with an adequate level of educational and methodological support has arisen. This article discusses the experience of creating new multiple-choice questions and assignments for students in the subject of theoretical mechanics.

Key words: student, theoretical mechanics, dynamics, new problem, assignment, test problem, quantity of motion, kinetic energy, theorem, change.

Author Z.S. Makhmudov has developed new multiple-choice questions and assignments for students in the theoretical mechanics department. The collection of questions and assignments compiled for the statics and kinematics departments has been approved by the ministry and recommended for publication as a textbook. The work on compiling questions and assignments for the dynamics department has been completed.

The new questions offered to students have been compiled as multiple-choice questions. This allows the teacher to give students individual problems to solve. Below is a new question recommended for students from the dynamics department:

1.4. Issue. A material body is falling down a steep inclined plane that makes an angle α with the horizon (Figure 1). If its initial velocity is g and the coefficient of friction is f , how long will it take the body to cover a distance s ? The quantities needed for the calculations are given in Table 1.4.

Table 1.4

No	α degree	v_0 m/s	s m	f -
1	30	2	4	0,12
2	45	6	12	0,16
3	60	4	8	0,1
4	15	12	36	0,15
5	25	20	44	0,2

Figure 1.4

Also, students were offered test questions prepared for the sections of theoretical mechanics. These test questions determine the level of their mastery of the curriculum, their competence and knowledge. Below is a test question prepared for the section of dynamics:

2.24. Test-issue. Which of the following answers correctly states the formula for the theorem on the change in momentum of a material point?

- A) $\frac{mv_1^2}{2} - \frac{mv_0^2}{2} = A(\vec{F})$
- B) $\vec{F} + \vec{N} + \vec{\Phi} = 0$
- C) $m\vec{a} = \vec{F}$
- D) $m\vec{v}_1 - m\vec{v}_0 = \vec{S}$

The creation of new multiple-choice (25-choice) tasks for students ensures that all students can solve the problem individually or perform computational and graphical work. Below is a task for students to apply the basic theorems of point dynamics. Students are shown one version of this task. This will be useful for students to work out their options.

Task D3

Application of theorems on the change in momentum and kinetic energy of a material point

Task D3. A material point with a mass m , starting from point A, moves at a speed $F=F(t)$ along a rough inclined plane forming an angle α with the horizon in time t_1 under the influence of a variable force (Figure D3). In the section AB, in addition to the force of gravity, the friction force also acts on the material point. The friction coefficient is equal to f . The material point starts moving at a speed from point B and moves down along a rough inclined plane forming an angle β with the horizon. In the interval BD, the material point is acted upon by the force of gravity, the force of friction, and the constant force P . Using the basic theorems of point dynamics, it is necessary to find the speed of the material point at point B and the speed of point C when it has traveled a distance S in the interval BD. The quantities required for calculations are given in Table D3.

Instructions

Task D3 is a task to apply the basic theorems of point dynamics - the theorem on the change in the momentum of a material point and the theorem on the change in the kinetic energy of a material point. When completing the task, pay attention to the following:

1. Apply the theorem on the change in momentum of a material point for an interval where the time of movement is known.

2. Apply the theorem on the change in kinetic energy of a material point for intervals where the distance is known.

Table D3

Variant number	Numerical values								
	m	$F=F(t)$	t_1	v_A	α	f	β	P	S
1	1	0,5t	2	2	15	0,09	60	2	3
2	2	3t	3	1	20	0,1	58	4	5
3	0,5	5t	1,5	1	25	0,11	54	7	9
4	3	7t	2	2	30	0,08	52	9	11
5	2	9t	3	3	36	0,12	45	11	13
6	0,8	2t	2	2,4	40	0,07	46	3	4
7	4	T	1	5	42	0,13	39	5	6
8	6	8t	4	4	45	0,06	37	8	10
9	12	5t	2,5	6	48	0,14	30	14	16
10	15	3t	1,5	10	52	0.15	29	17	19
11	9	2t	1	8	56	0.16	27	10	13
12	8	6t	0,5	6	60	0,18	25	9	10
13	5	T	4	3	55	0,17	20	6	7
14	3	12t	3	2	50	0.19	15	4	5
15	0,5	10t	2	1	45	0,2	22	1	2
16	0,6	9t	4	1,8	40	0,11	34	1,4	2
17	2	7t	5	3	35	0,09	43	3	4
18	4	5t	6	5	30	0,12	58	5	6
19	6	0,8t	7	7	25	0.08	52	8	9
20	10	2t	8	9	20	0,13	49	13	15
21	9	4t	2	10	15	0.07	59	11	13

22	11	3t	3	12	28	0,14	47	14	16
23	5	6t	4	6	34	0,06	40	6	8
24	0,9	4t	5	3	47	0,15	38	2	3
25	1	8t	6	2	51	0,16	53	2,2	3

Figure D3

In conclusion, the structure of the new multiple-choice questions and assignments for students fully meets the requirements of today. Because the existing sets of questions and assignments have become outdated in some sense. The solutions to many of them have already appeared on the Internet. Therefore, there is a need for new questions and assignments. We hope that the new set of questions and assignments, compiled by the author Z.S. Makhmudov and successfully applied in the educational process by senior teacher I. Najmiddinov, will be useful to everyone.

References:

1. Gafurovich, D. U., & Sotivoldievich, Z. M. (2021). The use of non-conventional power sources is a requirement of the period. *Academicia Globe*, 2(07), 121-126.

2. Mahmudov, Z. S., Daminov, J. A., & Rahimov, A. M. (2018). The Use Of Cluster Method In Lectures On Theoretical Mechanics. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) Vol, 27*, 145-147.
3. Mahmudov, Z. (2021). Application Of Venn Diagrams In Lectures On Theoretical Mechanics. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) Vol, 24*, 219-222.
4. Sotivoldievich, Z. M. (2021). A Way To Increase Students Activity In The Organization Of Lectures. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) Vol, 25*, 90.
5. Махмудов, З. С., & Дехканов, У. Г. (2021). Повышение благосостояния народа-основная цель государства. *Электронный инновационный вестник*, (3), 12-14.
6. Mahmudov, Z. S., & Najmiddinov, I. B. Improving the quality of education on the basis of demonstrations in lectures. *International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) Vol, 27*, 80-85.
7. Sotivoldievich, Z. M. (2021). A Method of Assessing Students' Knowledge in Practical Classes. *Design Engineering*, 9573-9578.
8. Sotivoldievich, Z. M., & Rakhimdjanovich, K. V. (2021, December). Demonstration in improving the quality of education. In *Conference Zone* (pp. 304-308).
9. Sotivoldievich, Z. M., & Rakhimdjanovich, K. V. (2021). The Problem Of Organizing Exhibitions Of Theoretical Mechanics Lessons. *Design Engineering*, 9569-9572.
10. Sotivoldievich, Z. M. (2021). About a new way of assessing students' knowledge in lectures. *International Engineering Journal for Research & Development*, 6(5).

11. Abduvalievich, D. J., Sotivoldievich, M. Z., Mutalovich, R. A., & Biloldinovich, N. I. (2022). ON THE ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE IN THE LESSONS OF STRUCTURAL MECHANICS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11, 14-20.
12. Sotivoldievich, M. Z. (2022). The use of venn diagrams in independent study of theoretical mechanics. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11, 192-197.
13. Sotivoldievich, Z. M., & Rakhimdjaniyov, K. V. (2021). About the Method of Assessing Students' Knowledge. *Design Engineering*, 9579-9585.
14. Махмудов, З. С., & Даминов, Ж. А. (2022). НАЗАРИЙ МЕХАНИКА ФАНИ ДАРСЛАРИНИ КЎРГАЗМАЛИ ТАШКИЛ ЭТИШ МАСАЛАСИ. *Scientific progress*, 3(4), 709-715.
15. Махмудов, З. С., & Аъзамов, К. С. (2022). О НОВОМ СПОСОБЕ ОЦЕНКИ ЗНАНИЙ СТУДЕНТОВ НА ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЙ МЕХАНИКЕ. *BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI*, 850-854.
16. Sotivoldievich, M. Z. (2022). AN EFFECTIVE WAY TO ASSESS STUDENT KNOWLEDGE. *Journal of Pharmaceutical Negative Results*, 756-761.
17. Mahmudov, Z., Najmiddinov, I., & Yuldasheva, B. (2022). USING THE CONFUSED LOGICAL CHAIN METHOD IN ASSESSING STUDENT KNOWLEDGE. *Solution of social problems in management and economy*, 1(7), 4-12.

- 18.Sotivoldievich, M. Z. Mutalovich RA ABOUT A WAY TO EVALUATE STUDENTS'INDEPENDENT LEARNING. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN, 2277-3630.
- 19.Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Azamov, K. S. (2023). USING THE CLUSTER METHOD FOR CONDUCTING LECTURES ON THEORETICAL MECHANICS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 *Impact Factor: 6.876, 17(02), 1-5.*
- 20.Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Mutalovich, R. A. (2023). ABOUT A METHOD OF EVALUATING STUDENTS'KNOWLEDGE IN THEORETICAL MECHANICS LECTURES. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 *Impact Factor: 6.876, 17(02), 6-12.*
- 21.Махмудов, З. С., & Рахимов, А. М. (2023). Применение метода кластер для проведения лекционных и практических занятий. *IQRO, 2(2), 239-242.*
- 22.Махмудов, З. С., & Аъзамов, К. С. (2023). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ДИАГРАММЫ ВЕННА НА ЛЕКЦИОННЫХ ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЙ МЕХАНИКЕ. *IQRO, 2(2), 248-251.*
- 23.Mahmudov, Z. S. (2022). Isaboev Sh. M., Abdujabborov AA, Rakhmatillaev YN Use of Modern Methods of Assessing Students' Knowledge. *Undishapur Journal of Microbiology, 15(1), 3280.*
- 24.Mahmudov, Z. S., & Najmiddinov, I. B. (2023). MILLIY AN' ANALARGA ASOSLANGAN "USTOZ-SHOGIRD" TIZIMIDAN FOYDALANISH. *IQRO, 2(2), 330-334.*
- 25.Mahmudov, Z. S., Tillaboev, Y. K., & MA'RUZA, M. U. M. H. USULIDAN FOYDALANISH//IQRO JURNALI.–2023. T, 2, 604-608.

26. Mahmudov, Z., & Ahmadaliev, K. M. (2009). On a way to increase the activity of students in the organization of lectures on theoretical mechanics. In *Proceedings of the International Scientific and Technical Conference "Modern Problems of Mechanics"*, Tashkent (Vol. 2, pp. 381-383).
27. Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Mutalovich, R. A. (2022). ABOUT A WAY TO EVALUATE STUDENTS' INDEPENDENT LEARNING. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH* ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429, 11, 165-170.
28. Махмудов, З. С. (2023). НАЗАРИЙ МЕХАНИКА ФАНИ КИНЕМАТИКА БЎЛИМИ МАВЗУЛАРИНИ ЎҚИТИШДА ИННОВАЦИОН ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАР.
29. Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Mutalovich, R. A. (2023). ABOUT A METHOD OF EVALUATING STUDENTS' KNOWLEDGE IN THEORETICAL MECHANICS LECTURES. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 17(02), 6-12.
30. Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Azamov, K. S. (2023). USING THE CLUSTER METHOD FOR CONDUCTING LECTURES ON THEORETICAL MECHANICS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES* ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 17(02), 1-5.
31. Махмудов, З. С., & Даминов, Ж. А. (2023). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ НА ЛЕКЦИОННЫХ ЗАНЯТИЯХ ПО ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЙ МЕХАНИКЕ. *Экономика и социум*, (4-2 (107)), 650-654.

- 32.Махмудов, З. С., & Карабаева, М. У. (2023). НАЗАРИЙ МЕХАНИКА ФАНИ ДАРСЛАРИ САМАРАДОРЛИГИНИ ОШИРИШНИНГ БИР УСУЛИ ТЎҒРИСИДА.
- 33.Dehkanov, U. G., Makhmudov, Z. S., & Azamov, Q. S. (2022). Practical Equation of Torque for a Concave Wing Rotor Drive. *Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal*, 1(6), 230-234.
- 34.Dehkanov, U. G., Makhmudov, Z. S., & Azamov, Q. S. (2022). General Equation of the Moment of a Concave Wing. *Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal*, 1(6), 70-74.
- 35.Sotivoldievich, M. Z. (2023). ASSESSMENT OF STUDENTS'KNOWLEDGE IN CLASSES USING THE METHOD OF CONFUSED LOGICAL CHAINS. *ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*, 12(07), 12-21.
- 36.Sotivoldievich, M. Z. (2023). AN EFFECTIVE WAY TO ASSESS STUDENT KNOWLEDGE IN THEORETICAL MECHANICS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 17(07),
- 37.Sotivoldievich, M. Z., & Mutalovich, R. A. (2023). USE OF VENN DIAGRAM POSSIBILITIES IN ORGANIZATION OF LESSONS OF THEORETICAL MECHANICS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429*, 12(08), 27-32.
- 38.Sotivoldievich, D. M. Z., & Kenjaboevich, D. T. Y. (2023). PRACTICAL CLASSES ON THEORETICAL MECHANICS ARE ORGANIZED IN A VISUALLY APPEALING MANNER. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(10).

39. Махмудов, З. С., & Даминов, Ж. А. (2023). ПРИМЕНЕНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ СТРАТЕГИЙ ПРИ ПРОВЕДЕНИИ ЛЕКЦИОННЫХ ЗАНЯТИЙ ПО ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКОЙ МЕХАНИКЕ. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(10).
40. Махмудов, З., & Najmiddinov, I. (2023). NAZARIY MEKANIKA FANI MA'RUZA MASHG'ULOTLARIDA KLASTER USULINI QO'LLASH TAJRIBASIDAN. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar*, 1(31).
41. Sotivoldiyevich, M. Z. (2023). USING THE KLISTER METHOD IN TEACHING THE KINEMATICS DEPARTMENT OF THEORETICAL MECHANICS. *International journal of advanced research in education, technology and management*, 2(11).
42. Mahmudov, Z., Raximov, A., & A'zamov, Q. (2023). NAZARIY MEKANIKA FANI DARSLARINI QIZIQARLI TASHKIL ETISHNING BIR USULI TO 'G 'RISIDA. *Talqin va tadqiqotlar*, 1(31).
43. Sotivoldiyevich, M. Z., Abduvaliyevich, D. J., Mutalovich, R. A., & Saidmamatovich, A. K. (2023). Application of The Method of Confused Logical Chain to Determine The Level of Students' Knowledge. *Journal of Advanced Zoology*, 44(S6), 829-834.
44. Sotivoldiyevich, M. Z., & Raximdjanovich, X. V. (2023). ABOUT THE APPLICATION OF THE " TANGLED LOGICAL CHAIN" METHOD IN CLASSROOM ACTIVITIES. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 17(12), 33-36.
45. Sotivoldiyevich, M. Z. (2024). USING THE POSSIBILITIES OF THE CONFUSION LOGIC CHAIN METHOD IN ASSESSING STUDENTS'KNOWLEDGE. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EUROPEAN RESEARCH OUTPUT*, 3(5), 165-174.

- 46.Sotivoldievich, M. Z. (2024). FROM THE EXPERIENCE OF MAKING MULTIPLE OPTION PROBLEMS ON THE DEPARTMENT OF STATICS OF THEORETICAL MECHANICS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EUROPEAN RESEARCH OUTPUT*, 3(5),
- 47.Sotivoldievich, M. Z. (2024). COMPOSITION OF MULTIPLE OPTION PROBLEMS ON THEORETICAL MECHANICS. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF EUROPEAN RESEARCH OUTPUT*, 3(5), 187-195.